

The Challenge of the Bucket Wash

Creating Desirable Sustainable Practices

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Abstract: the workshop ‘Creating Desirable Sustainable Practices; the Challenge of the Bucket Wash’ offers the opportunity to engage in the emerging realm of ‘practice-oriented design’, and to explore the tension between sustainability and desirability. Practice-oriented design builds design and research approaches on practice theory (from sociology) which takes practices – such as bathing or cooking – as its main unit of analysis. It offers a framework for understanding what goes on in people’s daily activities- routines, habits, et cetera. This is not only interesting for taking a different look at user experiences, but also for tackling issues of sustainability. To make this abstract topic tangible, a case is introduced using existing research on bathing. The ‘bucket wash’ concept boldly represents a way of bathing that is clearly less resource intensive than the currently dominant practice of showering *and* poses challenges for desirability.

Key words: *practice theory, practice-oriented design, sustainability, desirability, bathing.*

1. Introduction

The growing field of sustainable design has recently attracted much attention. This year, for example, is the first time that sustainability is officially a topic in the conference on Design & Emotion. Encouraged by a broader recognition and demand, Design for Sustainability is transforming rapidly while it slowly moves into the mainstream of design. Within sustainable design, reducing household resource consumption is an important concern. The focus thus far has been on making appliances more resource efficient through both technical improvements and embedding of more efficient use patterns through the scripting of user interactions [1]. Examples of ‘sustainable’ products, in the bathing sector are low-flow showerheads or the more recently introduced recycle showers, and feedback devices such as timers or tiles which change color in long, hot showers. In spite of these efforts, however, energy and water consumption of households is still growing. In the EU, annual growth in electricity consumption was 2.1 percent per year between 1990 and 2005 despite a decrease in average specific consumption of 1.5 % per year in the case of refrigerators, freezers, washing machines, dishwashers, TVs and dryers [2]. Energy savings through increased efficiency are outweighed by increased intensity of use and an ever growing array of household appliances.

It becomes increasingly clear that technical fixes alone will not solve the problem. What these approaches seem to lack are ways to deal with the mutual dependency of technology and behavior, by looking beyond isolated interactions between individuals and single products and toward the dynamics of everyday life. Specifically, they seem to be at a loss when it comes to the shifting standards and changing behavioral patterns that lie at the basis of continuing increases in resource consumption. Practice-oriented design, a relatively novel design approach informed by practice theory, offers a framework for tackling these complex issues of consumption within sustainable design efforts.

2. A practice orientation

With a dispersed history in sociological theory, practice theory shifts the focus of analysis from individual users and objects toward the social nature of routines, habits, expectations, skills, and material infrastructures which shape the daily practices in which these individual users and objects come together. Practices, such as bathing, cooking and doing laundry become the main unit of analysis [3].

According to practice theory, practices consist of a set of interconnected elements that can be summarized as conventions, competences and material artefacts [4] or in short: image, skill and stuff. Image elements are socially shared ideas that give meaning to the practice. In cooking, for example these could be ideas of health, enjoyment and sociality. Skills are learned physical and mental routines. In cooking, this is for example the know-how of baking an egg, but also the ‘need’ for potatoes in one and rice in other cultures. Stuff represents the orchestra of things involved in a practice. The stuff of cooking includes pots, pans, stove, tap, counter, food products, microwave, knives, cutting board, and so on.

Characteristic of practices is that they are both stable and dynamic. To use the same example, cooking, has existed since the invention of fire and is performed in all cultures. On the other hand, cooking as a practice has changed considerably over the at least 200.000 years it has existed [5] and large differences exist between cooking in different (cultural) groups. In terms of practice theory these dynamics consist of the making and breaking of connections between and within the different elements (image, skill and stuff). Product innovations play an integral role in this process, both actively and passively.

To focus on practices – rather than on products, people or contexts of use – has far reaching consequences for the design process. Practice-oriented design is still in its infancy, but it has the potential to deeply change design approaches, especially when it comes to social and environmental concerns [6-7]. These concerns are inherently collective and systemic and are therefore difficult to address by a focus on isolated interactions.

3. Sustainability and Emotion

Efforts to establish less resource intensive practices, to ‘downsize’ consumption for the sake of sustainability, are often seen as requiring personal sacrifices and generating negative experiences. For example, low-energy lifestyles are often associated with a reduced quality of life, conjuring up images of discomfort, inferior taste, environmental freaks and moldy smells. It is clear that the negative emotional associations with sustainability pose a great challenge to sustainable design: detaching displeasure and discomfort from reduced consumption, or, in other words, making sustainable lifestyles desirable.

Practice-oriented design and design for sustainability, however, tend to neglect the crucial aspects of emotion and experience that make interactions pleasurable. Our scope in this workshop at the Walhalla of Design & Emotion,

is thus to explore the question of how environmentally-preferable practices can become genuinely desirable drawing on the theoretical resources of practice theory and the design expertise of the participants. The question will be explored through an example of bathing.

4. Resource Consumption in Bathing

The workshop will draw on a year long study by the conveners, including four closely related design projects on the practice of bathing. The projects include two 'experiment'-studies, each involving 10 to 15 participants who experimented with their bathing practice at home [8-9], one detailed cultural inquiry about bathing in India, Japan and The Netherlands [10] and an explorative co-design exercise in cooperation with an industry partner [11]. One important conclusion from these studies was that current bathing practices in Europe are highly resource intensive and moving into directions that are increasingly so. A major culprit in this unsustainable practice is the paradigm of continuously flowing water, inextricably bound up with the dominant European bathing practice, showering. Showering is, for many, a very pleasant activity, offering functions like caring for one's body, waking up, relaxing and getting warm or refreshed. However, water from a shower touches the body only for seconds and then disappears down the drain, still warm and practically clean. Moreover, current developments in bathing do not offer much prospect of improvement. Power showers, massage showers and rain showers discharge ever growing flows of water while shower frequency and duration are increasing.

5. Bathing Differently

The studies into bathing practices looked for feasible, alternative ways of bathing that were less resource intensive than showering. Diving into the history of bathing and bathing in other cultures taught us to see showering in a different light. Although daily showering is the norm in Western Europe and the US, it has become so only during the past fifty years and is not so common in other modern cultures, like Japan. Furthermore, when experimenting with their own way of bathing at home, people came up with ways of bathing that abandoned the shower paradigm partly or even completely. From these studies we can conclude that showering is not the only possible way of bathing; people are willing and able to bathe in different ways. After assessing the user experiences and resource requirements of different ways of bathing, a concept here referred to as 'bucket wash' emerged as a promising direction in terms of user acceptance and resource consumption. The 'bucket wash' represents a way of bathing in which water is contained in a bucket sized container.

From initial research it is clear that the bucket wash is not immediately appealing to people accustomed to showering. After trying it out, study participants experienced discomfort; this way of bathing is currently not supported by European bathroom designs. However, they also experienced their 'bucket wash' routine as rewarding, effective and relaxing. These results combined with stories from bathing in India and Japan lead us to believe that a shift away from expectations of continuous water flow is possible – if only it were designed well.

6. Conclusion

Reflecting back on the practice-oriented approach, we can conclude that the 'bucket wash' concept, or more generally, moving from a paradigm of flowing water to a concept of containing water, differs markedly from approaches taken by existing products on the market that aim to reduce water consumption from bathing. As explained earlier, these existing products are either technology oriented products like low-flow showerheads and

recycle showers or behavior oriented products like timers and feedback on water and energy use. All of these existing examples take the concept of showering (i.e. flowing water) for granted and all require sacrifices on comfort. Therefore, the 'bucket wash' concept, drawing on practice-oriented design, is illustrative for a novel direction in design for sustainable bathing. Taking such a direction suggests that desirability and sustainability may go together by proposing a different possible way of bathing as opposed to making our current ways of bathing less unsustainable.

7. The Challenge

The challenge to the workshop participants is to redesign the bucket wash for the 21st century; to transfer and extend the tools and processes that have been developed in relation to Design & Emotion to the design of a pleasurable bathing experience that is both low resource-intensive and desirable. Tackling the bucket wash challenge through quick ideation and mock ups will provide insights into how D&E expertise can be combined with practice-oriented design and thus help to fuse widely disconnected considerations of emotional and sustainable aspects of design. Participants in turn will be introduced to practice-oriented design, offering innovative perspectives for Design & Emotion. The outcomes of the workshop will be used as an integral part of ongoing PhD research on practice-oriented design for sustainability.

References

- [1] Akrich, M. "The De-Description of Technical Objects." In *Shaping Technology/Building Society: Studies in Sociotechnical Change*, edited by W. Bijker and J. Law, 205-24. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1992.
- [2] European Energy Agency. "Indicator: En18 Electricity Consumption [2008.11]." http://themes.eea.europa.eu/Sectors_and_activities/energy/indicators/EN18%2C2008.11.
- [3] Reckwitz, Andreas. "Toward a Theory of Social Practices: A Development in Culturalist Theorizing." *European Journal of Social Theory* 5, no. 2 (2002): 243-63.
- [4] Ingram, Jack, Elizabeth Shove, and Matthew Watson. "Products and Practices: Selected Concepts from Science and Technology Studies and from Social Theories of Consumption and Practice." *Design Issues* 23, no. 2 (2007): 3-16.
- [5] Wrangham, R., Jones, J. H., Laden, G., Pilbeam, D., & Conklin-brittain, N. (1999). The Raw and the Stolen: Cooking and the Ecology of Human Origins. *Current anthropology*, 40(5), 567-594.
- [6] Shove, Elizabeth, Matthew Watson, Martin Hand, and Jack Ingram. *The Design of Everyday Life*: Berg, 2007
- [7] Hielscher, Sabine, Tom Fischer, and Tim Cooper. "The Return of the Beehives, Brylcreem and Botanical! An Historical Review of Hair Care Practices with a View to Opportunities for Sustainable Design." In *Undisciplined! Design Research Society Conference 2008*. Sheffield Hallam University, Sheffield, UK: Design Research Society, 2008.
- [8] Scott, Kakee. "Co-Designing Sustainable User Practices." MSc thesis, Delft University of Technology, 2008.
- [9] Kuijer, Lenneke, and Annelise de Jong. "A Practice Oriented Approach to User Centred Sustainable Design." In *Sixth International Symposium on Environmentally Conscious Design and Inverse Manufacturing* 541-46. Sapporo, Japan: The Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2009.
- [10] Matsuhashi, Noriko, Lenneke Kuijer, and Annelise de Jong. "A Culture-Inspired Approach to Gaining Insights for Designing Sustainable Practices." In *EcoDesign 2009: Sixth International Symposium on Environmentally Conscious Design and Inverse Manufacturing* 547-52. Sapporo, Japan: The Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2009.
- [11] Karakat, Harish. "Designing for Alternative (Sustainable) Bathing Practices." MSc, Delft University of Technology, 2009.